

Wear Resistance of Magnesium Alloy under Lubrication and its Surface Modified by Laser Texturing

Prem Ananth M^{#1}, Sivaramapandian J^{#2}, Anandha praba R^{*3}, Hari Kiran M G^{#4},
Harish Madhavan S^{#5} and Indrakanth N R^{#6}

^{#1,2,4,5,6} Department of Mechanical Engineering, Sri Venkateswara College of Engineering,
Pennalur, Sriperumbudur Tk. – 602117, Taminadu, India.

^{*3} Department of Electronics Engineering (VLSI Design and Technology), S.A. Engineering
College, Poonamallee, Avadi main road, Thiruverkadu, Chennai-600077, Tamilnadu, India.

Received: May 25, 2026

Accepted: Jun 18, 2026

Published: Jun 19, 2026

Abstract— This investigation aimed to study the potential of surface modified AZ31B-Magnesium Alloy for artificial knee joint applications. Traditional implant materials such as Titanium and Stainless steel alloys have long been favoured for their mechanical strength and corrosion resistance. However, their relatively high density and limited biocompatibility cause significant drawbacks. Magnesium alloys, particularly AZ31B, have emerged as promising alternatives due to their low density, excellent biocompatibility and mechanical properties. Despite their inherent tendency to corrode in physiological environments, this limitation can be significantly improved through surface modification techniques such as texturing and coating. In this work, coating is applied to improve the corrosion resistance by plasma techniques and surface texturing is employed to enhance wear resistance by modifying the surface by laser. The tribological performance of all the treated surfaces is evaluated by pin on disc experiment under simulated physiological conditions using synthetic synovial fluid, which closely reproduce the atmosphere of a human knee joint articulation. The study aimed to analyse whether AZ31B, with suitable surface modifications, be capable of serving as a lightweight and biocompatible alternative for materials currently used in knee joint implants.

Keywords— AZ31B-Magnesium alloy, artificial knee joint, implant materials, plasma coating, laser surface texturing, synthetic synovial fluid, biocompatibility, wear and corrosion resistance

I. INTRODUCTION

Knee implants replace damaged joint areas to reinstate its function and mobility. Components must resist load, motion, and biological interaction. AZ31B, due to its light weight and biocompatibility is being considered for such roles. However, uncoated magnesium alloys lack sufficient durability. This study focuses on modified AZ31B magnesium alloys to meet implant demands, offering better wear and corrosion performance while maintaining physiological compatibility for long term achievement in total knee arthroplasty.

Surface engineering enhances the properties of base materials by modifying only the surface, without altering their bulk properties [12]. This is predominantly important in biomedical applications without altering the core mechanical integrity of an implant material while optimizing its surface interactions [13]. In implant applications, surface engineering is used to improve the wear resistance, reduce friction, and enhance corrosion resistance factors that directly influence the implant longevity and patient life style [14]. Common implant materials such as stainless steel, titanium alloy, cobalt-chromium, tantalum, and various grades of polyethylene and ceramics. Each material is selected due to their strength, biocompatibility, and price. Magnesium alloys like AZ31B, though not widely used, are under investigation for their biodegradability and low density [3,5]. When protected by advanced coatings and surface texturing, they can be made suitable for implant requirements, making AZ31B as a next-generation material for orthopaedic applications.

For magnesium alloys like AZ31B, surface treatments are essential due to their high corrosion susceptibility [6]. Plasma electrolytic oxidation (PEO) forms a ceramic-like oxide coating on the material surface, significantly increasing its corrosion resistance by acting as a shield against body fluids. On the other hand, laser surface texturing introduces micro dimple patterns that reduce the wear rate by providing uniform load distribution at the contact region and enhancing lubrication retention during joint articulation [9].

Titanium Dioxide (TiO_2) is a commonly used ceramic kind of coating material known for its excellent hardness, high wear resistance, chemically stable, and excellent biocompatibility, making it suitable for biomedical applications. In implants, TiO_2 serves as a protective layer to minimize friction, resist corrosive body fluids, and enhance surface integrity during relative motion. It also possesses a high dielectric constant which can act as a barrier to ion and electron transport, which promotes corrosion protection capabilities of substrates over which it is being applied.

The methodology involves a systematic approach to assess the tribological behavior of AZ31B magnesium alloy for total knee joint replacement applications. The surface of AZ31B pins was modified using Laser Surface Texturing (LST) followed by the application of biocompatible coatings through plasma spray technology. These modifications were analyzed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM). Tribological performance was assessed using a pin on disc tribometer under simulated body fluid environment. Finally, wear and friction data were evaluated to analyze the effect of surface treatments on implant performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Laser Surface Texturing (LST)

The laser surface texturing (LST) process is a multi-step procedure that involves design, preparation, parameter selection, and precise execution. It begins with creating the desired micro-dimple or pattern geometry using computer-aided design (CAD) software such as EZCAD. These designs are then imported into the laser marking machine interface, where processing parameters such as power, frequency, and scanning speed are defined based on the material type and desired texture.

The specimen is then fixed onto the laser platform, and its surface is aligned using the Z-axis adjustment to maintain an optimal focal distance between the laser head and the surface, typically around 320 mm.

Figure. 1 20 kW powered Laser Machine used for Magnesium Alloy Texturing

Once aligned, the laser system emits focused pulses of high-energy light at a specific wavelength (1064 nm for Nd:YAG lasers), which interact with the material's surface. This interaction results in localized melting or ablation, creating precisely shaped dimples or grooves. The control over pulse repetition rate, beam power, and scanning speed allows for accurate control over dimple depth, diameter, and spacing. The process is efficient, repeatable, and clean, with no post-processing required.

Figure 2. Laser Textured Pin of 10 mm Diameter and 28 mm Length

2.2 Wear Resistant Titanium Dioxide (TiO_2) Coating

TiO_2 coating was employed as the top protective layer over Magnesium Alloy AZ31B pin specimens, using Plasma Spray Technology. The main objective was to improve the tribological performance of AZ31B, which, although mechanically compatible with bone due to its low density and elastic modulus, suffers from poor corrosion and wear resistance. To overcome this, a two-layered coating system was adopted. Before the deposition of TiO_2 , a Nickel-Chromium (Ni-Cr) alloy bonding coat was applied. Ni-Cr serves a dual purpose: it provides a ductile, thermally compatible transition layer between the AZ31B substrate and the hard TiO_2 ceramic, and it ensures excellent adhesion by establishing a strong metallurgical bond. The presence of Ni-Cr also enhances resistance to oxidation and prevents coating delamination during service.

Figure 3. TiO_2 Coated Mg AZ31B Alloy Specimen (a). Coating on bare Magnesium Alloy (b). Coating on Textured Magnesium Alloy

The TiO_2 coating, deposited over the Ni-Cr bond coat, was applied with a typical thickness ranging from 40 to 60 microns, while the bond coat thickness was approximately 10 to 20 microns.

2.3 Pin on Disc Wear Testing

In pin-on-disc tribological testing, the pin specimen represents the mobile part in contact with the stationary disc, simulating joint articulation. The selected pin material for this investigation is Magnesium Alloy AZ31B, chosen for its relevance in bio-implant applications. According to ASTM G99 standards, pin specimens used in pin-on-disc wear tests are typically cylindrical or spherical in shape. For this investigation, materials were procured in the form of rods and subsequently machined into pin specimens. Each pin was machined to a length of 28 mm and a diameter of 10 mm to ensure consistency and compatibility with the test setup. The tests were conducted with the following conditions: Normal Load: 100 N; Sliding Velocity: 1.25 m/s; Testing Time: 20 minutes.

To evaluate the sliding wear behavior of Magnesium Alloy (AZ31B), pin-on-disc wear testing was conducted using AZ31B pin specimens against a rotating EN31 Stainless Steel disc. During the test, the pin specimen was held stationary while the disc rotated under controlled conditions. The tests were carried out at room temperature in both dry (unlubricated) and wet (lubricated with Bovine Serum Albumin) environments to simulate physiological joint conditions.

to continuously measure frictional force and wear. Each AZ31B pin specimen was clamped in a vertical holder, pressing against the horizontally rotating cast iron disc. For every individual test, a fresh surface of the pin and disc was used to avoid cross-contamination and ensure accuracy.

Prior to testing, all pin and disc specimens were thoroughly cleaned with acetone to remove traces of grease and other contaminants. A new wear track diameter was selected for each run to expose the pin to a fresh disc surface. Three sets of trials were conducted using the AZ31B specimens in three surface conditions:

Untextured

Untextured and Coated (TiO₂ over Ni-Cr bond coat via Plasma Spray)

Textured (via Laser Surface Texturing)

Textured and Coated (TiO₂ over Ni-Cr bond coat via Plasma Spray)

2.3.1 Dry and Wet Wear

The wear specimens were tested under dry (unlubricated) and wet (lubrication with Bovine Serum Albumin) conditions at room temperature. The experimental setup of pin on disc under dry wear and wet wear conditions are shown in Figure 4 as (a) and (b).

Figure 4. Pin on disc wear test experimental setup (a). Under Dry Sliding Contact (b). Under Lubricating Contact

The pin specimen is made of Magnesium Alloy AZ31B, and the rotating disc is composed of EN31 steel, chosen to replicate the mechanical interaction between implant and counter face materials in total knee joint replacements. Overall, pin-on-disc testing is a fundamental step in preclinical evaluation, bridging the gap between material development and clinical application.

Frictional force and wear data were simultaneously acquired in real-time using integrated data acquisition systems, such as force sensor and linear variable differential transformer (LVDT). The amount of wear was determined by measuring the weight of the pin specimen before and after testing using a high-precision digital balance. The measured variables are plotted in Figures 5 and 6 with respect to sliding time to observe the progression of wear and variation in frictional force over time for each surface condition.

Figure 5 Sliding Friction Vs Sliding Time at 100 N normal load and 1.25 m/s

Figure 6. Sliding Wear Vs Sliding Time at 100 N normal load and 1.25 m/s

3. Results and Discussion

Laser processing generally results in a reduction of the coefficient of friction (μ), although the degree of effectiveness varies significantly across different specimen pairs. The most pronounced decrease was observed in specimen pair Mg+T+C and next to the above was Mg+T. However, the effect was minimal in specimen pairs Mg and Mg+T, showing higher friction values as compared to remaining two specimens. These results highlight the selective efficiency of processing in lowering friction depending on the material pairing.

Table 1 presents the wear test data obtained for all four specimen pair. The table includes the specific wear rate for each specimen. The tribological performance of both untextured and textured AZ31B specimens was analyzed and compared. The processing treatment demonstrates a significant enhancement in the wear resistance of materials, as evidenced by the consistent reduction in Specific Wear Rate (SWR) across all four tested specimen pairs. The reduction in SWR ranges from approximately 87 % in specimen pair Mg+T to an impressive 23 % in specimen pair Mg+T+C as compared bare magnesium alloy. The coating on magnesium alloy without texturing observed as a high wearing nature as compared with other combinations tested under wet wear conditions

Table 1. Tabulation of Mass Loss, Volumetric Loss and SWR of Mg AZ31B Alloy

Specimen	Mass before test in gram (m_1)	Mass after test in grams (m_2)	Mass Loss (M) in g	Density (ρ) in g/cm ³	Volume loss (V) in mm ³	Specific Wear rate (SWR) in $\times 10^{-3}$ (mm ³ /N-m)
Mg	3.938	3.841	0.097	1.81	53.593	0.144
Mg + T	3.949	3.942	0.007	1.81	3.868	0.0187
Mg + C	3.98	3.86	0.12	1.81	66.298	0.187
Mg + T + C	3.92	3.872	0.048	1.81	26.519	0.111

Figure 7. Image of Texturing specimen after wet wear test

The wet wear test specimens are analysed with high magnified image analyser and its one of the image is shown in Figure 7. This image is belongs to textured magnesium alloy specimen. The debris formed during high contact relative motion is accumulated in the cavities which resulted in the resistance to three body abrasion. Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) is employed to map elemental distribution across a sample surface, enabling the identification of chemical changes resulting from various treatments. In this study, EDS is used to confirm the retention of critical coating elements such as titanium (Ti), nickel (Ni), and chromium (Cr) in tribologically tested regions. Additionally, it assists in detecting residues of

bovine serum albumin (BSA) particularly elements like carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and phosphorus (P) within lubricated wear tracks, providing evidence of tribo-film formation. An illustrative example is the use of EDX overlay on scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images, revealing Fe-Si rich zones corresponding to disc counter-body elements, indicating protective coating intact with the substrate and protect the magnesium alloy substrate area due to wear or delamination.

Figure 8. (a) SEM and (b) EDS mapping of Coated and Laser Textured Specimen

4. Conclusion

This research investigated the potential of surface-modified AZ31B magnesium alloy for application in artificial knee joint replacements. While traditional materials like Ti-6Al-4V and Co-Cr-Mo have been favored, AZ31B was explored as a promising alternative due to its low density, favorable mechanical properties, and excellent biocompatibility. The successful application of laser texturing and TiO₂ coating process on Magnesium Alloy AZ31B contributes to improving its wear resistance and frictional behaviour, making it suitable for biomedical applications like knee joint prosthetics. The 87% reduction in SWR in specimen pair Mg+TiO₂ showed exemplary performance as compared with other combinations tested under same tribological contact conditions. These results support the potential of surface-modified AZ31B as a lightweight and biocompatible substitute for conventional materials currently used in knee joint implants.

References

- [1] Y. Xin, T. Hu, and P. K. Chu, "(2011), In vitro studies of biomedical magnesium alloys in a simulated physiological environment: A review," *Acta Biomaterialia*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1452–1459.
- [2] G. Song and A. Atrens, (2003), "Understanding magnesium corrosion—A framework for improved alloy performance," *Advanced Engineering Materials*, vol. 5, no. 12, pp. 837–858.
- [3] Gray and B. Luan, (2002), "Protective coatings on magnesium and its alloys—A critical review," *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*, vol. 336, no. 1–2, pp. 88–113.
- [4] H. Hornberger, S. Virtanen, and A. R. Boccaccini, (2012), "Biomedical coatings on magnesium alloys—A review," *Acta Biomaterialia*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 2442–2455.
- [5] L. Zhu and G. Song, (2006), "Improved corrosion resistance of AZ31B magnesium alloy by an aluminium-alloyed coating," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 200, no. 8, pp. 2833–2840.
- [6] P. Fauchais and A. Vardelle, (2017), "Thermal sprayed coatings used against corrosion and corrosive wear," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 201, no. 5, pp. 1908–1921.
- [7] S. You, Y. Huang, K. U. Kainer, and N. Hort, (2017), "Recent research and developments on wrought magnesium alloys," *Journal of Magnesium and Alloys*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 239–253.
- [8] M. Multigner, E. Frutos, J. L. González-Carrasco, J. A. Jiménez, P. Adeva, and J. Chao, (2009), "Influence of the surface properties on the corrosion behaviour of magnesium alloys for biomedical applications," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, vol. 203, no. 20–21, pp. 3098–3104.
- [9] D. Thirumalaikumarasamy, K. Shanmugam, and V. Balasubramanian, (2020), "Influence of chloride ion concentration on immersion corrosion behavior of plasma sprayed alumina coatings on AZ31B magnesium alloy," *Journal of Magnesium and Alloys*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 456–465.
- [10] Song EP, Ahn J, Lee S, Kim NJ, (2008), Effects of Critical Plasma Spray Parameters and Spray Distance on Wear Resistance of Al₂O₃-8 wt.% TiO₂ Coatings Plasma-Sprayed with Nanopowders. *Surface and Coatings Technology*. 202(15):3625-3632.
- [11] Mao B, Siddaiah A, Liao Y, Menezes PL. (2020) Laser Surface Texturing and Related Techniques for Enhancing Tribological Performance of Engineering Materials: A Review. *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, 53:153-173.
- [12] Zhang E, Yin D, Xu L, Yang L, Yang K.(2009) Microstructure, Mechanical and Corrosion Properties and Biocompatibility of Mg–Zn–Mn Alloys for Biomedical Application. *Materials Science and Engineering C*, 29(3):987-993.

- [13] M. Geetha, A. K. Singh, R. Asokamani, and A. K. Gogia, (2009), "Ti based biomaterials, the ultimate choice for orthopaedic implants – A review," *Progress in Materials Science*, vol. 54, no. 3, pp. 397–425.
- [14] Q. B. Nguyen and M. Gupta, (2011), "Enhancing compressive response of AZ31B magnesium alloy using alumina nanoparticle reinforcement," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 71, no. 13, pp. 1465–1470.
- [15] A. Atrens, G. Song, M. Liu, Z. Shi, F. Cao, and M. S. Dargusch (2015), "Review of recent developments in the field of magnesium corrosion," *Advanced Engineering Materials*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 400–453, 2015.
- [16] Wang A, Essner A, Schmidig G, (2008), The Effects of Lubrication, Material, and Design on Wear of Orthopaedic Implants. *Journal of Materials Science: Materials in Medicine*, 19 (2):577-584.